

SELECTING APPROPRIATE METHODS BASED ON AGE CHARACTERISTICS

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***Annotatsiya.** Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda turli yoshdagi o'quvchilar va o'rganish uslublari uchun mos usulni qanday tanlash kerakligi tushuntiriladi.*

***Аннотация.** В этой статье объясняется, как выбрать подходящий метод преподавания английского языка для учащихся разного возраста и стилей обучения.*

***Abstract.** This article explains how to choose appropriate method for different age learners and learning styles in teaching English.*

It is true that education helps students to develop in all aspects, to become mature specialists in an important field in the future. At the same time choosing the most appropriate methods and styles depending on age characteristics in the process of school education this is considered the most basic way. Teaching methodology is the most basic part of the educational system, so a teaching method refers to the set of step by step procedures used by the teacher in guiding the learners to achieve learning objectives. I have to say that there is a large number of methods used in teaching different age group, according to academic research.

Linguistics have demonstrated that there is not one single best method contexts, and that on one teaching method is inherently superior to the others. Also it is not always possible or appropriate - to apply the same methodology to all learners, who have different ages, objectives, environments and learning needs. In fact selecting appropriate methods it is highly essential part, because choosing the appropriate teaching method brings instruction to life while encouraging students to actively engage with content and develop their knowledge and skill.

During the lesson, it is essential to keep in mind various characteristics of each students (level, age, etc). This method enables the teacher to develop a productive strategy for language learning with students. It is considered that learning foreign language regarded by children at an early age in many countries around the world. First children got to be successfully affected by language in learning it. One or two hours a weeks is not sufficient to achieve a good result. Naturally, children learn by interacting with objects they see and touch. This process is as significant as the formal clarification of the material, teachers ought to continuously pay attention to the age of the children. There is contrast receiving of information between a child of 5 and 10 years old.

Notes for teaching children

Change tasks often.

Combine study and play.

Pay attention to your English children imitate well.

We can use the following extensively and effectively in method selection.

1.DIRECT WAY METHOD

In this method the teaching is done entirely in the target language. The learner is not allowed to use his or her mother tongue. Grammar rules are avoided and there is emphasis on good pronunciation.

Essentials translation.

Teaching concepts and vocabulary through pantomiming, real life objects and other visual materials oral training helps in reading and writing grammar is taught indirectly.

GRAMMAR TRANSLATION METHOD

Learning is largely by translation to and from the target language, grammar rules are to be memorized and long lists of vocabulary learned by heart. There is little or no emphasis placed on developing oral ability. This method focuses on reading and writing only. As a result speaking and listening are overlooked.

AUDIO LINGUAL METHOD

The theory behind this method is that learning a language means acquiring habits. There is much practice of dialogues of every situation.

New language is first heard and extensively drilled before being seen in its written form. Drills and pattern practice are typical (Richards, J.C. et al. 1986): Repetition: The student repeats an utterance as soon as he hears it.

Inflection: one word in a sentence appears in another form when repeated.

Replacement: one word is replaced by another.

Restatement: the student rephrases an utterance.

TASK BASED LANGUAGE LEARNING

This method it is very useful to students, the focus of the teaching is on the completion of a task which in itself is interesting to the learners. Learners use the language they already have to complete task and there is little correction of errors. I have to say the task based learning (TBL) is all about your students creating, producing, or designing something in class, it could be anything at all.

The task based in essence, a language lesson based on the Task - based language teaching method has three stages, the PRE TASK ACTIVITY, the TASK and the POST TASK or REVIEW.

This is the predominant method in middle school ESL teaching at Frankfurt international school. The tasks are subsumed in a major topic that is studied for a number of weeks. In the topic of ecology, for example students are engaged in a number of tasks culminating in a poster presentation to the rest of the class. The tasks include reading searching the internet listening to taped material, selecting important vocabulary to teach other students etc. It is a strong and communicative approach where students spend a lot of time communicating. PPP lessons seem very teacher centered by comparison. Just watch how much time the students spend communicating during a task based lesson.

It is enjoyable and motivating.

ANOTHER BASIC IMPORTANT METHOD THE SILENT WAY.

This is called because the aim of the teacher is to say little as possible in order that the learner can be in control of what he wants to say. No use is made of mother tongue.

As the name implies, silence is key tool of the teacher in the silent way from the beginning levels, students do 90 percent or more of the talking.

Being silent moves the focus of the classroom from the teacher to the students and can encourage cooperation among them.

IN CONCLUSION: we should emphasize that choosing appropriate methods based on age characteristics greatly helps language learners to learn any foreign language quickly and qualitatively within a certain period of time. I have to say that above, we have provided some information on the teaching method and methodology related to age characteristics. In other words the use of this information and its practical use and application in the training process is the most important task of trainers.

In general, the most effective and useful way is to choose the appropriate method related to age characteristics.

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